

A Roadmap for Open Access Compliance in Publicly-Funded Research

Summary

Publicly funded research in India generates valuable knowledge, yet much of it remains locked behind journal paywalls—denying access to the very public whose taxes funded it. Although the DST and DBT adopted an Open Access (OA) Policy in 2014 mandating deposition of research outputs in open access institutional repositories, compliance has been inconsistent due to weak monitoring and a lack of robust repository infrastructure. This brief recommends that public funding agencies enforce two key measures:

- **Mandatory Deposit of Final Version of Articles in an OA Repository & Strengthening Repository Infrastructure**— Require Principal Investigators to deposit final accepted manuscripts from publicly funded projects in an institutional or national repository, with infrastructure strengthened to build a national repository system. Interim use of non-commercial, trusted international repositories is acceptable.
- **Compliance Statements in Final Project Completion Reports** – Mandate that project completion reports include a declaration of OA compliance, with URLs for deposited works in an institutional or national repository.

These measures will ensure public accountability, improve traceability of research outcomes, enhance societal impact, protect national knowledge sovereignty, and align India with global best practices in open science.

Introduction

Article 51A(h) of the Constitution of India identifies the development of scientific temper, humanism, and the spirit of inquiry and reform as a fundamental duty of every citizen. In line with this vision, the Government of India, through agencies such as the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Department of Biotechnology (DBT), and the newly established Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), invests significantly in exploratory scientific research. Each publicly funded project contributes to the creation of valuable new knowledge.

However, the benefits of this knowledge are often inequitably distributed, as research articles from publicly funded projects remain behind publishers' paywalls, restricting access for the general public whose taxes funded the research. The Open Access (OA) movement, catalyzed by the Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002) [1], followed by the Bethesda Statement (2003) [2] and the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities (2003) [3], created a powerful global discourse around the principle that publicly funded knowledge should be freely accessible to all.

These declarations not only established the normative framework for open access but also shaped national and institutional policies worldwide [4,5]. In India, the OA movement gained momentum in the early 2000s, with the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) among the first to adopt institutional OA mandates, thereby aligning the country with the global push for democratizing access to scientific knowledge.

To improve the accessibility of extramural projects funded by DST and DBT, these agencies in 2014 adopted an Open Access Policy [6]. The policy mandates that all articles arising from projects funded by these agencies must be deposited in a central or institutional open-access repository, ensuring wider dissemination and public availability of publicly funded research. However, implementation of this policy has remained inconsistent and unsatisfactory. There is currently no systematic mechanism to monitor whether outputs from publicly funded research are being deposited in open repositories. This lack of compliance undermines the policy's intent — ensuring public access to publicly funded research.

Moreover, without a national repository culture, much of India's publicly funded research continues to be accessible primarily through foreign commercial publishing platforms, posing challenges to national knowledge sovereignty. In the spirit of *Aatmanirbhar Bharat*, it is critical that India builds and strengthens its own systems for knowledge dissemination. To address this issue, this brief recommends that the DST, DBT, and ANRF implement clear, mandatory guidelines. These should require:

- The deposit of the final accepted manuscript(s) arising from publicly-funded projects in an open-access repository;
- The final project completion report must include an explicit statement confirming compliance with the Open Access mandate and provide the URL of the deposited manuscript(s).

Without these minimal compliance measures, the goal of making publicly funded research openly accessible and evaluating of impact of projects will largely remain unmet.

Policy Recommendations: A Closer Look

We recommend that DST, DBT, and ANRF adopt the following policy measures:

a) Mandatory Open Access Deposit & Development of Repository Infrastructure

Require that the final accepted manuscript of every research publication arising from public funding, such as DST-funded projects, should be deposited in a recognised institutional or national open-access repository immediately after acceptance. It is the responsibility of the Principal Investigator of the funded project to comply with this mandate.

Indian funding agencies must invest in building and maintaining a national infrastructure to support open access to research output. This could involve establishing dedicated national repositories or repurposing existing platforms such as [Science Central](#) or [IR@INFLIBNET](#) to function as a central repository for publicly funded research outputs.

Such a national repository could serve as a centralized national infrastructure and ensure all publicly funded research outputs are accessible in one place. In the absence of access to such a repository at this point, non-profit initiatives, such as PubMedCentral, Zenodo, arXiv, OSF, etc, can be used. The advantage of using these international repositories is that they assign each submission with persistent identifier (PID) such as a DOI, which then helps to access the particular item.

Additionally, while encouraging immediate deposition of manuscripts is ideal, it may conflict with the copyright and embargo policies of many journals. Therefore, INFLIBNET could establish a mechanism that automatically enforces publishers' embargo periods—such as releasing manuscripts after six months or one year, depending on the publisher's policy—ensuring compliance while sparing authors the additional time, effort, and potential legal complications of managing embargoes themselves.

However, it is essential to develop a national retention rights strategy to ensure legal and sustainable open access practices across institutions and disciplines, where papers can be made accessible immediately without facing any embargo period from publishers. DST-CPR, IISc has prepared a separate policy brief outlining key recommendations for implementing such a national retention strategy.

b) Mandatory Compliance Statement in Project Completion Report

Final project reports submitted to the funding agency (DST/ANRF) must include a statement using language such as:

“All peer-reviewed publications resulting from this project have been deposited in an open access repository, in accordance with the DST-DBT Open Access Policy.”

This declaration should be accompanied by the URL(s) of the deposited manuscript(s) in the repository, ensuring traceability, serving as a compliance mechanism, and enabling the tracking of Open Access outcomes.

Why This Is Needed: Key Rationale

- **Public Accountability:** Ensures that research funded by taxpayers is accessible to the public, policymakers, educators, and entrepreneurs.
- **Knowledge Traceability:** Requiring statements in final reports enables funding agencies to better track research outcomes and evaluate project success.
- **Maximizing Public Value:** Ensuring open access to publicly funded research enhances its reach, reuse, and societal impact.
- **National Knowledge Sovereignty:** Reduces dependence on commercial publishing platforms for accessing Indian research output.
- **Alignment with Global Standards:** Brings Indian science policy in line with global best practices in research openness and transparency.

International Precedents and Best Practices

- UKRI (UK Research and Innovation) mandates immediate open access deposit in repositories as a condition of funding. See: [UKRI Open Access Policy](#) [7].
- European Commission and ERC mandate OA with compliance statements in project reporting. See: [ERC Open Access Guidelines](#) [8].
- NSF's public access policy requires that certain publications and juried conference papers be deposited and made available within 12 months of publication in the [NSF Public Access Repository \(PAR\)](#). See: [NSF guidelines](#) [9].
- The 2024 NIH Public Access Policy requires Author Accepted Manuscripts accepted for publication in a journal, on or after July 1, 2025, to be submitted to PubMed Central upon acceptance for publication, for public availability without embargo upon the Official Date of Publication. See: [NIH Public Access Policy](#) [10].

Conclusion

To ensure transparency, traceability, and accessibility of research funded by public resources, DST and ANRF must update their grant conditions to include mandatory OA deposition, compliance reporting, and acknowledgment protocols. These actions will position India at the forefront of responsible research dissemination and strengthen the visibility and impact of its publicly funded science. However, there is a need for strengthening repository infrastructure to support better compliance.

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